

TECHNOLOGICAL EVOLUTION AND THE THREAT OF FAKE NEWS: PERSPECTIVES AND SOLUTIONS

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Abstract

Fake news is a global problem overgrowing in recent years and seems increasingly difficult to combat. From the 2016 US presidential election to the COVID-19 pandemic, then the two wars in Ukraine and now in Israel, the phenomenon has evolved into new forms. All have culminated in the emergence of highly advanced and sophisticated artificial intelligence tools that make misinformation increasingly challenging to detect. We are dealing with an unprecedented situation that affects democratic values and may trigger radical reactions in society with global effects, as happened in the outbreak of the conflict in Israel. In this article, we have conducted a theoretical analysis of how the fake news phenomenon has been amplified by artificial intelligence. In the face of these new challenges, quality journalism is essential, and the role of professionals in the field is more important than ever to reflect reality and combat fake news. The article is helpful for researchers in the field but also for communication and journalism professionals.

Keywords: fake news, artificial intelligence, democracy, communication, journalism

Introduction

In the 21st century, the phenomenon of fake news is one of the most challenging vulnerabilities to control “in the context of the accentuation of global problems” (Motoi G., 2020). Guess et al. (2018) explained in their study that during the 2016 election, when the level of fake news reached alarming heights, one in four US citizens had accessed a website spreading fake news. The estimate covered the last six months before the presidential election. The problem is exacerbated by social networks that are more likely to spread fake content (Vosoughi et al., 2018). Furthermore, the growth of social media in recent years has led to an exponential increase in fake news, in the Covid-19 pandemic

reaching a veritable "infodemics". Several researchers (Allcott & Gentzkow, 2017; Chadwick et al., 2018) have investigated the motivation behind the spread of misinformation's purpose, but also how it spreads. However, developing emerging technologies, especially language models, has amplified this phenomenon (Goldstein et al., 2023). Artificial intelligence has developed at a highly rapid pace (Stănescu G.C., 2023) and has revolutionized many aspects of our daily lives. Chatbot-like conversational applications have radically changed the way information is generated (Węcel, K., 2023), and this has created a high risk of misinformation and the spread of fake news. This phenomenon has become a primary concern in the digital age, and AI plays a significant role in intensifying this danger.

The phenomenon of disinformation in today's digital environment

The term fake news began to be used frequently after the 2016 US presidential election, but the term disinformation can be found long before that, specifically after World War II. The notion originated in the Russian language, and the role of the term was "to designate exclusive capitalist practices aimed at enslaving the popular masses" (Vulkoff, V., 2007). Nevertheless, it should not be forgotten that the first code of ethics of the media industry adopted by the Kansas State Editorial Association in 1910 refers to fake news (Oprea, B., 2021). Hunt Allcot and Matthew Gentzkow (2017) defined fake news as "News articles that are intentionally and verifiably false". Lazer et al. (2018) define fake news as "fabricated information that mimics media content in the form". Indeed, this phenomenon is a threat in modern society, where information is rapidly transmitted through digital sources and can create confusion and manipulate public opinion to gain an advantage or achieve a specific goal. Hendricks et al. (2018) mentioned that a characteristic of fake news is that it "poses as real news" but behind it aims to attract attention for a secret purpose. Vlăduțescu (2016) associates the concept of truth in relation to verisimilitude, i.e., "that which resembles the truth". Hence, we can say that because of the way we understand truth, we see Reality on our own, and the truth is actually "what we perceive true", as mentioned by Manjoo F. (2008).

In the current digital context, where we are witnessing a real technological explosion, fake news can take many forms, from fake news texts, fake images, truncated videos, and untrue statements attributed to people known to society or who might inspire trust. Information of this kind may give the appearance of trustworthiness. However, it may be distorted or even fabricated to manipulate public opinion, influence elections, or undermine trust in news institutions and organizations. According to Hendricks&Vestergaard (2018) those who spread fake news hide four main motivations: for trolling, for material benefit, for marketing and sales, and in the struggle to gain power. So, often, fake content is created and spread by individuals or entities who want to promote a specific agenda or draw attention to certain topics. Furthermore, artificial intelligence makes this much easier to achieve.

Artificial intelligence and fake news

Artificial intelligence has revolutionized multiple aspects of our lives, including how information is distributed and generated, and this technological advancement has exponentially increased the risk of spreading false information. Through applications of artificial intelligence, content generation can now be automated. Thus, fake news can be created extremely easily with chatbots, and information can reach the general public much more easily, and it is only one step from there to virality. Artificial intelligence-based language models are generally trained on texts available on the internet, and this allows for the automated generation of credible news. Moreover, by providing sufficient data, applications can create news reports, based on stories that appear natural and are written by humans, with sensational headlines and stories that are taken from online newspaper sections. So text-generating algorithms can create articles that look genuine, with meaningful content, making it increasingly difficult to discern between real and fake information. AI can also be used to personalize the content consumed by users, thus creating "information bubbles" in which people are exposed only to information that supports or reinforces their existing beliefs (Stănescu, G. C., 2023). At the same time, through artificial intelligence, images can be manipulated. Technologies that

generate photographs and video images can create faked clips that give the impression that they are real. This leads to situations where people or events can easily be faked, which can even have serious consequences for political and social stability.

Through AI, audio or video recordings can be created that appear to show real people in fictitious situations. Through deepfakes, a person can appear to say or do things they never actually did. It can be used to manipulate public opinion and compromise someone's reputation.

Conclusion:

Artificial intelligence has exponentially increased the risk of creating and spreading fake news. The phenomenon has evolved significantly in recent years and has taken on new dimensions, becoming a global problem that can significantly affect society and democracy. Intelligent tools have made disinformation increasingly challenging to detect, and often actual facts are called into question. From influencing election results to fuelling tensions in international conflicts, fake news has become a powerful weapon that has swept the globe. In the face of this threat, policymakers and social networks, as well as society as a whole, must work together to develop solutions to combat this phenomenon. At international level, a number of institutions are working on strategies and measures to combat this phenomenon, but it does not seem very easy to find a concrete solution. In this context, quality journalism plays a crucial role. Professionals in the industry must respect professional ethics and thoroughly verify the news they publish.

References:

- Anna Elisabetta Galeotti & Cristina Meini (2022) Scientific Misinformation and Fake News: A Blurred Boundary, *Social Epistemology*, 36:6, 703-718, DOI: 10.1080/02691728.2022.2070788
- Allcott H., Gentzkow M. (2017). Social media and fake news in the 2016 election. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 31(2), 211–236.
<https://doi.org/10.1257/jep.31.2.211>

- Chadwick A., Vaccari C., O'Loughlin B. (2018). Do tabloids poison the well of social media? Explaining democratically dysfunctional news sharing. *New Media & Society*, 20(11), 4255–4274. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444818769689>
- Dima, I. C., & Vlăduțescu, Ș. (2012). *Persuasion elements used in logistical negotiation: Persuasive logistical negotiation*. LAP Lambert Academic Publishing.
- Goldstein, J. A., Sastry, G., Musser, M., DiResta, R., Gentzel, M., & Sedova, K. (2023). Generative language models and automated influence operations: Emerging threats and potential mitigations. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2301.04246>
- Guess, Andrew, Nyhan, Brendan, Reifler, Jason, 2018. Selective Exposure to Misinformation: Evidence from the Consumption of Fake News during the 2016 U.S. Presidential Campaign. European Research Council Working Paper.
- Haleem, A., Javaid, M., & Singh, R. P. (2022). An era of ChatGPT as a significant futuristic support tool: A study on features, abilities, and challenges. *Benchmark Transactions on Benchmarks, Standards and Evaluations*, 2(4), 100089
- Li, J., & Su, M.-H. (2020). Real Talk About Fake News: Identity Language and Disconnected Networks of the US Public's "Fake News" Discourse on Twitter. *Social Media + Society*, 6(2). <https://doi.org/10.1177/2056305120916841>
- MacDonald, N., Holmes, K. L., & Kho, A. (2023, April 3). An exploratory survey about using ChatGPT in education, healthcare, and research. *medRxiv*, 3.
- MOTOI, G. (2020). The Challenges And Opportunities Of Green Economy And Green Jobs. From A Global To A European Approach. *Social Sciences and Education Research Review*, 7(2), 195-205.
- Porumbescu, a. (2022). Covid-Pandemic Related Restrictions on the Freedom of Circulation in Europe. *Revista Universitară de Sociologie*, 18(3).
- Stănescu G. C (2023) The impact of artificial intelligence on journalism. adverse effects vs. benefits, *Social Sciences and Education Research Review*, 10(1) 258–262. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8151135>
- Vosoughi, S.; Roy, D.; Aral, S. The spread of true and false news online. *Science* 2018, 359, 1146–1151.

- Vladimir Vulkoff (2007) *Tratat de dezinformare De la calul troian la internet*, Antet Revolution
- Vlăduțescu Ș. (2006) *Comunicare jurnalistică negativă (Convicțiune și persuasiune - eseu de hermeneutică mediatică)* Editura Academiei Române, București
- Węcel, K., Sawiński, M., Stróżyna, M., Lewoniewski, W., Księżniak, E., Stolarski, P., & Abramowicz, W. (2023). Artificial intelligence-friend or foe in fake news campaigns. *Economics and Business Review*, 9(2), 41-70.